

STRUCTURE-PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF TWO-DIMENSIONAL WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A revival of interest in woven composites is observed in recent years. However, the understanding of their elastic and strength behaviour is still in its infancy. Now, modeling starts with the creation of a geometric model of the fabric structure. This results in an automated partition of the unit cell, the local fibre volume fractions, and the yarn orientations. Through the application of a Fabric Geometry Model, the full set of elastic constants is obtained. A parametric study was performed to understand how the different geometric parameters of the fabric can be combined to determine the elastic behaviour of the composite material.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, woven fabric composites are widely used in technical practice, especially in the field of aerospace, marine and sports technology. This is because of their favourable mechanical properties. Moreover, the fabric is an attractive reinforcing textile because of its ease of handling and low fabrication cost. Fabrics can be woven from materials as glass, carbon, kevlar and space-age ceramics. The woven fabric geometry can be easily altered to meet the mechanical requirements of the composite material. The variables under control include the fibre and resin type, the yarn type and the weave type. Therefore, it is important to understand how the properties of the constituting phases, and the geometric characteristics of the fabric, combine to determine the properties of the final composite material.

Previous studies in this area have been largely concerned with the prediction of the in-plane elastic properties. Ishikawa and Chou [1-2] developed three models to predict the thermo-elastic behaviour of various woven fabric composites: the mosaic model, the crimp model and the bridging model. Those models are *one-dimensional* models because they neglect the two-dimensional extent of the fabric i.e. the undulation of the yarns running perpendicular to the loading direction is always neglected. The *two-dimensional* analysis of Naik and Shembekar [3-4-5] considers the undulation of the yarns in both warp and weft direction. An important trend marking the development of mechanical models is the more detailed geometric description. Now, a *three-dimensional* analytical model is presented to analyse the geometric characteristics and to predict the full set of elastic constants for laminae based on a general weave geometry.

GEOMETRIC AND ELASTIC ANALYSIS

The composite is idealised by a regular, periodic array of material unit cells. After carrying out an extensive geometric analysis of the fabric, a library of 108 subcells was put together to describe different unit cells. Next, each subcell is divided in 4 or 50 sub-subcells to describe the undulation of the yarns (fig. 1). Even the most complicated woven structures can be described by those subcells. The complexity arises from the possible presence of combined yarns or super yarns in the fabric composite. The presence of those super yarns in the skin of real 3D woven core sandwich composites was theoretically predicted and experimentally confirmed. Special subcells, containing pile fibres of 3D-sandwich-fabrics, were developed to extend the model [6-7]. The geometric model, based on a lenticular yarn cross-section, predicts the local fibre volume fractions within the different sub-subcells, the yarn orientations and the cover factor.

Figure 1. Three-dimensional micromechanical analysis of woven fabric composites.

The fabric architecture is defined by a set of geometric parameters. Even for simple woven constructions, important geometric differences exist between the warp and the weft direction. Subscripts w for warp yarns, and f for filling yarns are used. The pick lengths or yarn spacings p_{ww} and p_{ff} are constant linear measures. Because the interlacing of warp and weft yarns causes thread flattening, a lenticular yarn cross-section is assumed. The aspect ratio f of each type of yarn is defined as the width w over the thickness t of the lens.

$$f = \frac{w}{t} \tag{1}$$

The width and thickness of each yarn can be expressed as a function of aspect ratio f , number of filaments N_f , diameter of one filament d and filament packing factor K . A crimp parameter h is defined for warp and weft yarns (fig. 2). Its value corresponds to the distance between the mid-plane of the lamina and the top or bottom of the corresponding yarn. Thus, if h_f equals zero, then the filling yarns show no undulation. It is clear that the crimp parameters for warp and weft yarns are coupled parameters (eqn. 2). The increase of undulation in one direction of the fabric, reduces the undulation in the other direction.

$$h_f + h_w = t_f + t_w \tag{2}$$

The thickness of the fabric can be expressed as a function of the yarn thickness t and the yarn crimp parameter h :

$$D_{fabric} = MAX(t_w + h_w, t_f + h_f) \quad (3)$$

A modified Fabric Geometry Model [8-9] is used to calculate the three-dimensional stiffness matrix, and thus all the engineering constants of the composite unit cell. There are two basic assumptions. First, each sub-subcell is treated as a unidirectional lamina. The elastic properties of the laminae are calculated based on the local fibre volume fraction of the considered sub-subcell. Second, the material stiffness properties of the unit cell are the weighted sum of the stiffness properties of all sub-subcells i.e. a constant strain is assumed for all sub-subcells. The weight of each cell is given by its fractional volume to the unit cell. The stiffness matrix of the composite unit cell $[C_T]$ can then be written as follows:

$$[C_T] = \sum k_i [T_{\epsilon,i}]^T [C_i] [T_{\epsilon,i}] \quad (4)$$

where $[T_{\epsilon,i}]$ is the transformation matrix for yarn system or sub-subcell i , $[C_i]$ the stiffness matrix of a unidirectional lamina, and k_i is the fractional volume of sub-subcell i

Figure 2. Geometry and notation for a 2D fabric composite.

A custom MS-Excel® application, called WC40, has been written to perform all geometric and elastic calculations. Different dialog boxes are used to provide the input or to show the geometric and stiffness results. This application also includes macro sheets that can calculate the yarn-orientation-distribution function and the sub-subcell composition for each given unit cell. Not only standard weave styles such as plain, twill and satin, but also self-designed fabrics can be treated by the model. Because of the use of this powerful spreadsheet program, it is easy to add missing aspects such as graphs, to exchange data with other applications or to link a database with material property data.

PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS

Through the construction of structure-performance maps and process-windows, the relative effectiveness of various woven reinforcements can be assessed. In this paper, process-windows are calculated using WC40 for a one-layer plain woven fabric composite. These windows are bounded by the condition of circular yarns (as the minimum aspect ratio=1) and the condition of impossible interlacing of yarns. All geometric and elastic input is given in table 1. A fibre diameter d of 0.01 mm and a fibre packing density K of 81 percent was used in all calculations. This high intra-yarn fibre volume fraction K corresponds to a hexagonal closed packing of the fibres in the yarn. Notice that the crimp parameter h for the weft yarns is set equal to the thickness t . Then, since both yarn systems have the same size, one can easily see from eqn. 2 that they have also the same undulation. The elastic material parameters are the isotropic glass fibre properties and the epoxy matrix properties.

Table 1. Geometric and elastic input.

Composite	plain weave ($E_{\text{fibre}}=73$ GPa, $v_{\text{fibre}}=0.2$ and $E_m=3.13$ GPa, $v_m=0.34$)			
Thickness D	$=\{D_{\text{fabric}} = \max(t_w+h_w, t_f+h_f)\}$			
Yarn	N_f	d (mm)	K	$h/2$
warp	415	0.01	0.81	-
filling	415	0.01	0.81	$=\{t_f/2\}$

The format of this parametric study is to lower the yarn spacing p until the geometric limit of the woven architecture is reached. The geometric limit is controlled by the condition of impossible interlacing of both yarn systems. Of course, the fibre content in the fabric is affected by this variation. Table 2 shows the different aspect ratios f used, and the corresponding limiting yarn spacing p_{limit} .

Table 2. Range of values for the aspect ratio and the yarn spacing.

Aspect ratio f	Yarn spacing p (mm)
1 (circular)	$4 \rightarrow 0.4$
5	$4 \rightarrow 0.6$
10	$4 \rightarrow 0.8$
20 (flat)	$4 \rightarrow 1.1$

Figure 3 shows the predicted global fibre volume fractions V_f of the fabric composites, calculated from the yarn and subcell dimensions. The higher the aspect ratio f , the higher the maximum fibre volume fraction. For very flat yarns, this maximum value reaches 54 percent. This is a rather low value compared to the high intra-yarn fibre volume fraction of 81 percent. The large differences in fibre volume fraction for the various aspect ratios are related to the difference in composite thickness.

The fabric or composite thickness D is only dependent on the yarn thickness t and the crimp parameter h , not on the yarn spacing p (fig. 4). The fabric thickness can be related to softness and insulation properties of fabrics.

The curves for the cover factor, herein defined as the projected yarn area to unit cell area ratio, are presented in figure 5. This parameter is of interest in studies of the porosity and the permeability of fabrics. For circular yarns, the maximum covering possible is about 80 percent. By flattening the yarn section however, a cover factor of 100 percent can easily be realised.

Figure 3. Computed fibre volume fraction as a function of yarn spacing p .

Figure 4. Lamina thickness of the plain woven fabric composite.

Figure 5. Computed cover factor of the plain woven fabric composite.

Through the application of the modified Fabric Geometry Model, the full set of elastic constants is obtained. The material unit cell of a fabric composite is defined by nine independent constants due to the geometric and material symmetries with respect to warp and weft direction. In figure 6, the predicted Young's moduli in warp (E_x) and weft (E_y) direction are plotted as a function of yarn spacing p . We observe that a flattening of the yarn section will lead to a higher maximum value. Close to the condition of impossible yarn geometry, small variations in yarn spacing p have an

important effect on the calculated moduli. We experienced that the difference between the curves is mainly caused by the difference in fibre volume fraction.

Figure 6. Elastic output: Young's moduli in warp(x) and weft(y) direction.

The maximum transverse shear moduli G_{yz} and G_{xz} decrease when flattening the yarns, whereas the maximum in-plane shear modulus G_{xy} increases (fig. 7 and 8). The prediction for the in-plane modulus is always lower than for the transverse moduli. Also the shear moduli are very sensitive to the yarn spacing p in the vicinity of the geometric limit of the fabric.

Figure 7. Elastic output: Transverse shear moduli.

Figure 8. Elastic output: In-plane shear modulus.

As is shown in figure 9, the through-thickness Poisson's ratios, v_{xz} and v_{yz} , vary significantly with varying aspect ratio f and yarn spacing p . Predictions are always higher than for the in-plane Poisson's ratio v_{xy} (fig. 10). The curves corresponding to low aspect ratios f , below five, show a remarkable dependence on the yarn distance. That is, the same Poisson's ratio can be reached with different values for the yarn spacing. Let us also point out that the Poisson's ratios of woven fabric composites can be much higher than the ratio for the pure matrix material ($v_m=0.34$), and also much lower than the ratio for the fibre material ($v_{fibre}=0.2$). The elastic constants of unidirectional laminae can be properly estimated from the fibre volume fraction. In general, for woven fabric composites with the same fibre volume content large differences exist due to the different microstructure.

Figure 9. Elastic output: through-thickness Poisson's ratios.

Figure 10. Elastic output: in-plane Poisson's ratio.

CONCLUSIONS

A fully three-dimensional micromechanical analysis was developed to predict the overall geometric and elastic properties. This analytical model that treats the fabric repeating cell as an assembly of subcells and sub-subcells, can handle standard weave styles such as plain, twill and satin, but also self-designed fabrics. The undulation and continuity of the yarns in warp and weft direction, the actual yarn cross-section, the crimp in warp and weft yarns, and the fibre packing factor have been considered in the analysis. A user-friendly custom Microsoft Excel® application, called WC40, was developed to implement the geometric and elastic model. Because of the use of

a powerful and flexible spreadsheet program, it is easy to add missing aspects, to exchange data or to link external databases with fabric or material property data.

A parametric study was carried out to construct process-windows for a plain woven fabric composite. Such windows are useful to study the effect of various parameters on the composite's properties. It appears that the aspect ratio f has a major influence on the fabric cover factor and on the fabric thickness. Because the thickness of the composite was set equal to the fabric thickness, the aspect ratio controls the fibre volume content. The accurate computation of fibre volume fraction is an essential part of the analysis. Also, the geometric limit of the woven fabric is very much dependent on the microstructural parameters. We see that close to this condition of impossible yarn geometry, small variations in yarn spacing p have an important effect on the calculated Young's moduli, shear moduli and Poisson's constants.

Now, work is focusing on the damage behaviour of fabric composites and on the implementation of strength calculations. The development of such modeling tools, will certainly provide increased flexibility in selecting the best fabric reinforcement for structural components.

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